

Affordable mobile learning: Conventional cell phones for English as a foreign language teaching

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Abstract. The increasing use of cell phones among teenagers and young adults has contributed to the growth of mobile learning in different educational fields, including English as a foreign language (EFL) teaching. However, many learners in Latin American countries have limited access to this new learning modality due mainly to economic factors. It is necessary to provide EFL students with affordable mobile learning activities that will allow them to enhance their language learning experience. The present paper addresses an overview of mobile learning, including definitions and learning theory approaches used in its implementation. After presenting several studies on cell phone use for EFL teaching, this paper discusses several alternatives to implement more affordable activities to students using conventional cell phones. The final sections present potential advantages and disadvantages of cell phones as teaching tools, ending with recommendations for possible implementations.

Resumen. El incremento en el uso de teléfonos celulares entre adolescentes y jóvenes adultos ha contribuido al aumento del aprendizaje móvil en distintos ámbitos educativos, incluyendo la enseñanza de inglés como lengua extranjera. Sin embargo, muchos estudiantes en países de Latinoamérica tienen acceso limitado a esta nueva modalidad de aprendizaje, debido principalmente a factores económicos. Es necesario asistir a los estudiantes de inglés con actividades de aprendizaje móvil asequibles para que puedan mejorar su experiencia de aprendizaje. El presente artículo muestra una visión general del aprendizaje móvil, incluyendo definiciones, y enfoques basados en distintas teorías del aprendizaje. Además de presentar estudios realizados con teléfonos celulares para la enseñanza del inglés como lengua extranjera, este artículo discute varias alternativas para crear actividades más accesibles a los estudiantes, usando teléfonos celulares convencionales. Las secciones finales identifican posibles ventajas y desventajas en el uso de teléfonos celulares como herramientas de enseñanza, terminando con sugerencias para una posible implementación.

Introduction

Mobile devices are changing the way we learn with technology, providing potential advantages that can be applied to the English language teaching field (Kukulsma-Hulme & Shield, 2008). The use of mobile technologies around the world has grown rapidly in the last decade with mobile cellular subscriptions globally increasing from 12% in the year 2000 to approximately 67% in 2010 (ITU, 2010). The most popular mobile devices, cell phones, have also been the most used in studies on mobile learning (or m-learning) for English as a foreign or second language (Cui & Wang, 2008; Meurant, 2007; Cavus & Ibrahim, 2007). English as a foreign language (EFL) means that English is learned in a country where it is not the official or native language, it is taught within the learner's culture, and has limited opportunities to be used outside the classroom. English as a Second language (ESL) means that English is learned in a country where it is the official or native language, or is of general use within that country's culture, giving the opportunity to the learner to practice it outside the classroom (Nayar, 1997; Brown, 2000; 2001). Both terms have been used interchangeably in the literature reviewed to refer to English language teaching to non-native speakers. The term EFL as used in this paper will refer to the teaching of English language, irrespective of the terms used by the authors in their articles.

Cell phones, called mobile phones in Europe, are electronic portable devices primarily designed for communication purposes. Today, cell phones differ from earlier models in that many new features have been added, making these devices more versatile. For the purpose of this paper, cell phones will be classified in conventional cell phones and smart phones, considering their design and affordability. In general, low-cost cell phones with basic features are known as feature or conventional cell phones. These basic features include voice messaging, text messaging, picture camera, video and audio recording, Bluetooth and sometimes internet access for browsing (Lu, 2008; Cui & Wang, 2008; Ekong, 2008).

Smart phones are defined as “integrated communications devices that combine telephony, computing, messaging, and multimedia (Wagner, 2005, p.44). They are usually seen as devices that combine features from a conventional cell phone and a portable digital assistant (PDA). Two important differences between conventional cell phones and smart phones are that smart phones work through an operating system (OS) and run native applications (applications already installed in these devices).

The majority of studies on the use of cell phones for EFL have been developed in countries of East Asia, Europe or Africa, with activities and applications on smart phones or sophisticated cell phones that usually require internet access to be implemented (Orr, 2010). The use of cell phones in most Latin American countries increased over a 100% by 2008. However, mobile broadband subscriptions (internet access through cell phones) accounted for only 11% in Latin America and the Caribbean, compared to 89% in North America (ITU, 2009). Consequently, implementing similar studies in Latin American countries would represent a challenge for learners with limited internet access. Other alternatives should be considered to make mobile learning activities in EFL courses more accessible in these countries.

Adolescents and young adults in Latin America represent the sector of the population with the highest use of cell phones (ITU, 2008; Bahamóndez, Doring & Schmidt, 2009). Today, cell phones play an important role in teenagers’ everyday activities, not only for oral communication, but also as a tool to monitor their social life and relationship with peers (Campbell, 2005). Depending on the cell phones’ capabilities, teenagers can keep in touch with friends, through text or instant messaging for example, as well as to include people who share their interests in their networks.

Since teenagers and young adults carry their cell phones with them almost all the time, these technologies offer a potential opportunity to help the youth learn anywhere they are. Smart phones and cell phones with access to internet

offer a wide range of potential uses in EFL, such as mobile version of language dictionaries and English courses applications, among other options. However, many language learners cannot afford smart phones with data plans to access Internet for learning content.

The following sections will present an overview on mobile learning, a term that has emerged from the use of mobile technologies for teaching and learning. The paper also discusses the role of mobile devices in EFL learning, especially cell phones, at different educational levels. Alternatives to implement affordable mobile learning activities with conventional cell phones are also described. Lastly, the paper identifies potential advantages and disadvantages of using cell phones as teaching tools, ending with recommendations for future implementations.

What is Mobile learning?

Advocates of mobile learning do not agree on a single definition due to the rapid development of the field, as well as the different connotations given to the term “mobile” (Kukulka-Hulme, 2009; Caudill, 2007; Traxler, 2009; Rajasingham, 2011). Chinnery (2006) defined mobile learning as a subdivision of e-learning, whereas Corbeil and Valdes Corbeil (2007) stated that it was a combination of mobile computing and e-learning. Lu (2008) defined it as ‘learning assisted by mobile technologies’ (p. 515). For Kukulka-Hulme & Shield (2008), mobile learning is learning through handheld devices that may be available in any place, at any time. Caudill (2007) defined this modality as “any e-learning application delivered on-demand via mobile digital device” (p.3). Sandberg, Maris and Geus (2011) defined mobile learning as “the acquisition of knowledge through a mobile device” (p.1335).

Traxler (2009) considered some definitions in the field as very broad and imprecise, like the one presented by the Mobile learning network (MoLeNET) that defined mobile learning as “exploitation of ubiquitous handheld hardware,

wireless networking and mobile telephones to enhance and extend the reach of teaching and learning” (as cited in Traxler, 2009, p. 3). He argued that mobile learning’s definition should be limited to those devices that can be carried in a handbag or a pocket, and defines it as the use of PDAs/palmtops/handhelds, smart phones and cell phones to provide education and training. It can be inferred from all these definitions, that in order for mobile learning to take place, the use of portable and mobile electronic devices has to be involved. Therefore, the term mobile learning as used in this paper will be defined as learning with the assistance of a small portable electronic device available to the learner when needed.

Learning approaches to Mobile Learning

Approaches to learning have developed rapidly in the past twenty years, moving from behaviorist to cognitive and constructivist perspectives, with technology playing an important role along the way (Herrington, Herrington & Mantei, 2009). The advances in technology have helped classroom teaching tools to evolve from the use of classic chalk and blackboard, to the use of audiovisual materials, and eventually to the inclusion of computers, projectors and smart boards in the classroom. This progression has contributed to moving traditional classroom instruction from teacher-centered to student-centered, allowing students and teachers work together in order to achieve learning objectives. With the arrival and increase use of mobile technologies, learning can be taken out of the classroom, providing educators with the opportunity to apply existing approaches to the use of mobile devices for educational purposes.

Naismith, Lonsdale, Vavoula and Sharples, (2004) addressed how the major learning theory approaches have been applied to learning activities and projects with mobile devices:

- Behaviorism: mobile devices facilitate teacher’s feedback and positive reinforcement about students’ progress.

- Constructivism: mobile devices provide engaging experiences, letting students build their own learning at their own pace.
- Collaborative learning: mobile devices are means of communication and electronic information that can be shared with others.
- Situated learning: mobile devices can be used in real learning settings. Students can relate what they are learning to their daily activities.
- Informal and lifelong learning: learning takes place anytime and our environment has an influence on it.

Other precursors of mobile learning have also found its application to different learning approaches in EFL. Read (as cited in Lu, 2008) presented a behavioral approach to mobile learning, stating that empirical studies on vocabulary learning demonstrated that the systematic approach (learning vocabulary by memorizing target language words together with native language translations) benefits vocabulary development. Sending students vocabulary words with their translation to their cell phones through text could be an example for this approach.

Cavus and Ibrahim (2008) applied two learning approaches to mobile learning: informal learning and constructive learning. They considered mobile learning as ‘informal’ because it can happen at anytime, anywhere. Mobile learning is also ‘constructive’ because people construct their knowledge from their own experiences. Social-constructivist theories of learning can also be applied to mobile learning because it is “more personalized, ubiquitous and user-centered” (Motiwalla, 2005, p. 582). For instance, tasks with mobile devices can help students construct their knowledge about food concepts in English. Instead of reading in the textbook how to prepare an American dish, the teacher can assign students to prepare their favorite American food and record it on video with their cell phones, smartphones or iPods. In the next class, they export it to the class computer (if available) or exchange it through Bluetooth.

Rajasingham (2011) considered that a constructivist, interactive and self-directed learning is supported by teaching with mobile technology, as an expansion of traditional e-learning settings. Adult EFL learners with tight schedules can access their learning material from their mobile devices without the restriction of time and place, taking charge of their learning's pace.

As seen above, researchers take different positions on the application of learning theory approaches in teaching with mobile technology. Each of these approaches may have an application when designing mobile learning tasks in EFL, considering the factors that affect EFL learning, such as student's learning style and cognitive abilities, age, personality and socio-cultural factors. Teaching and learning with mobile devices allow teachers and students explore options to make the teaching-learning process more meaningful, within the different learning theory categories. On the one hand, a behaviorist example can be listening to the traditional "repeat after me" drill activity, still popular among EFL teachers, but through an audio-lesson in an iPod or recorded on a cell phone. On the other hand, a constructivist example could be a "scavenger hunt" during recess time, when students need to find the items corresponding to a list of new words sent to their cell phones in a text message.

Mobile Devices in mobile learning

What types of devices are mobile? Like the term mobile learning, the criteria to identify a device as mobile vary among authors. Trifanova and Ronscheti (as cited in Kukulsma-Hulma, 2009) defined a mobile device as any small and autonomous device that we can carry all the time without being noticeable. Mobile devices may include hand-held and laptop computers, portable digital assistants (PDAs), audio and video players (mp3 players, dvd players, ipods), handheld video consoles (nintendo DS, PSPs), digital dictionaries, e-book readers, smart phones, and cell phones (Chinnery, 2006; Stockwell, 2010; Cui & Wang, 2008; Meurant, 2007; Corbeil & Valdes-Corbeil, 2007).

Among the variety of technologies considered as mobile, some not necessarily meet the definition mentioned in the previous paragraph. Some authors argue that although the terms portable, mobile and handheld have been used interchangeably to refer to these technologies, there is a difference among them (Traxler 2009; Caudill, 2007). For instance, laptops, notebooks and tablet PCs are handheld, but they cannot be considered mobile devices because they are not small enough to fit in a pocket. In addition, these devices are usually turned off while users are in motion, which is not the case of mobile devices like cell phones.

iPods, PDAs, handheld computers, tablet PCs and especially cell phones, are the most commonly used devices in mobile learning language activities, whether in formal or informal settings (Chinnery, 2006; Corbeil & Valdes-Corbeil, 2007; Kukulsma-Hulme & Shield, 2008). For example, MP3s players can be used to listen to podcasts of English lessons downloaded from internet, as well as songs and audio dictionaries. iPods can be used to download audio-video lectures as well as e-books, and their recording feature can be used to record dialogues to assess students' listening skill and pronunciation. PDAs were initially used as translators, but today their use offer more advantages with the design of language learning programs (Thornton & Houser, 2005). Besides the potential advantages offered by handheld computers with internet access, the keyboard and screen make them suitable for language learning with written activities that require students' information input. Tablet PCs basically provide the same options of a laptop computer, but their smaller size makes them easier to use in mobile learning activities.

Cell phones are probably the most widely used mobile devices around the world (Ekong, 2008; Cui & Wang, 2008). In general, the student population owns more cell phones than computers, mostly due to their affordability, and this is one of the reasons why researchers consider them helpful to improve students' motivation toward language learning (Cavus & Ibrahim, 2008). In a pre-study questionnaire, all students in a preparatory school of a university in Turkey had at

least one cell phone, while less than half students had personal computers (Saran, Kursat & Seferoglu 2008). Similar results were found in a study carried out with students in a vocational high school in Taiwan, where 137 students admitted to have at least one cell phone, while only five did not have them all the time (Lu, 2008).

According to results of surveys by Pew Internet (2010), on average, 80 % of American teens between 14 and 17 years old own a cell phone. Although cell phones have become part of the lives of younger generations, their use for educational purpose in elementary and high schools in the United States is very limited, and research on their educational impact has been scarce (Campbell, 2005).

Cell phones in language learning

Research on the use of mobile devices in education has not been very extensive (Saran et al, 2008), but a fair number of studies and projects have been carried out using cell phones for language learning purposes. The Stanford Learning Lab developed one of the first projects in this area, designing Spanish learning material to be delivered via voice and e-mail in cell phones (Brown as cited in Chinnery, 2006). Initial results of the experiment were not satisfactory due to irregularities in voice and audio features, and problems with internet connections. However, it was found that simple chunks of instruction sent to students' cell phones increased their motivation to learn Spanish. Outside the United States, research on mobile learning using cell phones has been conducted to teach languages, such as Dutch, Portuguese, French, and mostly EFL. Studies have been implemented in European, East Asian and African countries at elementary, secondary and higher educational levels.

Studies on cell phones at Elementary and Secondary schools

Studies on cell phone use for language learning, including EFL, have been

conducted in elementary and secondary education. For instance, in an effort to raise Irish students' interest in their once native language, the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment in Ireland carried out a pilot project where high school students would learn Irish using their mobile phones and web-chat (Cooney & Keogh, 2007). The results indicated that both students and teachers perceived improvement in speaking Irish after participating in this project. Moreover, students found the use of technologies more stimulating than conventional teaching.

In another research, the Dutch Early Bird foundation in the Netherlands conducted a study in which fifth grade students used smart phones applications to learn English vocabulary (Sandberg et al, 2011). In order to show evidence of these devices' efficacy, children were divided into three groups: 1) children who used traditional materials, 2) children who used smart phones in activities at school and in the field trips, and 3) children that took smart phones home for the two weeks that the study lasted. The authors concluded that children in the third group -who spent more time with the smart phones- learned significantly more and achieved better results in the post-tests than children in the other two groups.

Furthermore, Lu (2008) analyzed the effectiveness of short vocabulary lessons when delivered to EFL students' cell phones through short-message-service (SMS). In a study with Chinese high school students, he found that students who read SMS lessons recalled more vocabulary than those who read them in paper based material. He also observed that students felt more motivated using this technology as a medium for self-learning.

Studies on cell phones in higher education

In higher education, research on the use of mobile devices for EFL has been conducted on a larger scale than elementary and secondary education. In Turkey, Basoglu and Akdermir (2010) conducted a study about the effectiveness of cell

phone applications compared to traditional flashcards for English vocabulary learning in first year college students. Although both techniques yielded satisfactory results, students that used cell phones obtained higher scores in the post-tests and reported they felt more motivated for learning.

Many studies on mobile language learning have focused on the short-service-message (SMS) and e-mail features to deliver English vocabulary words to students. Saran et al. (2008) conducted a study where they created instructional materials and sent them to Turkish prep school students through SMS and mms(multimedia messaging), to improve their vocabulary acquisition. The results showed that using mobile phones to deliver these instructional materials enhanced students' motivation, and improved their vocabulary.

Cavus & Ibrahim (2009) used SMS supported by a system they developed to teach new technical English words to first-year Turkish college students. The findings showed that participants enjoyed the new way of learning outside the classroom and were satisfied with what they had learned. Also, results in post tests showed that average scores increased considerably, suggesting that there was a significant improvement in their vocabulary. In a similar study conducted in Japan, students' cell phones received text messages and emails related to EFL learning activities through a software developed for these purposes (Thornton & Houser, 2005). Results presented that students who preferred their cell phones over desktop computer to work on the activities, reported more improvement in their learning.

Kiernan and Aizawa (2004) also used cell phones to teach EFL to Japanese college students, this time through task-based learning activities. Students were divided into three groups: 1) using cell phone email features, 2) using PC email, and 3) using face to face conversation. Besides students' learning improvement, this study also researched the platform preference. All members in the face to face conversation group finished the tasks on time, while only some in the PC and cell phone email groups finished their tasks in the time given. However, the

results in the post-tests showed a significant improvement in the cell phone group in comparison with the other groups, as well as students' satisfaction in using cell phones in the activity.

Research on use of cell phones at a college level has also been conducted for languages other than English. For instance, Moura and Carvalho (2010) affirmed that SMS represented an effective tool in language teaching after using this feature to assist Portuguese and French languages teaching to young adults learners in Portugal. The results showed that most students had positive attitude toward this teaching modality and obtained considerable improvement in their language learning.

In some studies, researchers also reported limitations and drawbacks. For instance, in Kiernan and Aizawa's study, the group performing the speaking activity was supposed to do it over the phone, but students could not afford the high costs in phone calls, and changed the strategy face to face conversations. In a class of 31 students participating in Lu's study, one student did not carry a cell phone on a regular basis, so his data was excluded from the study (Lu, 2008). A drawback in most studies for potential generalization is that programs and applications were developed by the researchers specifically to implement the studies. It is possible that some of these programs were not used again once the studies were over. This factor would represent a challenge if similar research is intended to carry out in Latin American countries. However, the positive results reported in general suggest that cell phones may be effective tools for EFL learning, with the design of mobile learning strategies that match the possibilities of teachers and learners in their own environment.

Mobile learning in Latin America

Projects

With the rapid development of mobile learning in the United States and

countries in Europe, East Asia and Africa, and the implementation in Latin America is taking off. Higher education institutions in some Latin American countries have developed projects in mobile learning for online courses. For instance, the Universidad de San Buenaventura in Colombia developed a mobile learning project in which students could access educational content through their cell phones or pocket PCs (Jiménez, Cortés, Martin & Lozano, 2007). The project consisted in the design of a mobile learning management system that could be accessed from mobile devices supporting java applications. The authors indicated that the mobile application allowed students interact with the content in a user-friendly way. Trials showed that the applications worked regardless the mobile device, but the layout of the information varied due to the devices' configuration.

Similarly, the Instituto Tecnológico de Monterrey in Mexico, started in 2008 a project called "Tecnología Educativa para el Aprendizaje Móvil" (Educational Technology for Mobile Learning), which has improved and expanded gradually (www.ccm.itesm.mx/techmovil). The project consisted in the design of a mobile learning management system for the delivery of online courses through Blackberry smart phones. Participants in the project are also conducting research evaluating the effectiveness of mobile devices for educational activities.

In some Latin American countries, it seems that mobile learning in higher education has been used as a mobile modality of electronic learning, where students use their cell phones to access online material. However, this type of mobile learning is not accessible to all students because is mostly promoted by the use of cell phones requiring internet connections, usually smart phones.

Studies

Studies on mobile learning found in the literature are few, but it is possible that considerable research on this matter is taking place in some Latin American countries. Saccol, Schlemmer, Barbosa, Reinhard and Sarmiento (2009)

conducted a series of online, telephone surveys and face to face interviews about mobile learning practices in Brazil, and concluded that in both business and academia mobile learning's development is still in an early phase. According to them, there are challenges to overcome in different aspects, such as technological and economic limitations, and the opposition to embracing new technologies in learning.

Bahámondez, Doring, and Albrecht (2009) addressed the potential of cell phones as tools to teach impoverished children in underdeveloped Latin American countries. Based on the potential benefits of mobile computing technology in learning, they proposed a study in which 5th graders in a Panama's public school would practice basic math concepts (addition, subtraction, multiplication and division) using cell phones, through exercises developed with simple java applications.

Kim, Miranda, and Olaciregui (2008) presented a review of potential uses of mobile devices to teach underserved Latin American indigenous children to read Spanish, their native language. The authors presented a series of alternatives to provide these children with learning material for reading, using a mobile device similar to a cell phone. The authors also discussed some factors to consider when implementing this mobile learning technology. These factors included the type of mobile learning model, learning conditions, living conditions, and needs. Also, the design of the mobile device to be used should be sturdy but with a user-friendly interface. Kim et al. (2008) felt optimistic that a mobile learning project would be beneficial to improve the poor literacy conditions of people living in rural areas with little or no access to technology.

Authors in these three studies concluded that further investigation was needed due to the increasing use of mobile devices, especially cell phones. Furthermore, more effort should be directed toward these technologies in order to utilize their benefits in educational settings.

Mobile learning research on EFL in Latin America seems to be minimal

compared to other regions, according to a gap found in the literature after looking through different sources. In the studies presented, only Kim et al. (2008) addressed mobile learning for language learning. However, his purpose was to teach illiterate indigenous children to read in their own native language. This finding suggests that further research would be suitable to measure the effectiveness of mobile learning activities that do not require complex-technology.

Affordable mobile learning in EFL teaching

Although many results in research studies have shown the effectiveness of mobile devices in language teaching, the limited or lack of access to technology as well as the costs of high-tech mobile devices (Meurant, 2007; Elias, 2011) are among the reasons why mobile learning has not yet expanded in some Latin American developing countries. Implementing mobile learning strategies in English language instruction under these circumstances is challenging, but not impossible. Satisfactory results may be obtained if mobile learning activities are adapted to the technology available in order to meet the learners' needs (Caudill, 2007).

Two important elements must be taken into account in order to design effective instruction with mobile learning activities: the context and the learners (Dickerson & Browning, 2009). When adapting mobile learning for language teaching, teachers must consider the affordability of the technology adopted to create instructions that correspond with the learner's demands and the setting where language learning will take place.

Sharples (2006) defines context as "a dynamic entity, constructed by the interactions between learners and their environment" (p. 5). That is, mobile learning context links to other daily activities, like riding the bus and walking in the mall, among other activities. The mobile learners' context emerges from their social context; therefore, when designing mobile learning activities for EFL

teaching, it is necessary to have a clear picture of how and where learners will be interacting with the target language. EFL learners mostly interact inside the classroom and chances for further interaction decrease once classes are over. Most learners will not practice the target language outside the classroom, unless they are highly motivated. Thus, using devices that students are already familiar with is an innovative way to increase their motivation (Caudill, 2007). Teachers must be aware of the capability of the students' cell phones, verifying that they have the features that are intended to be used and students are able to perform the activities. Similarly, teachers must prepare activities taking into account other technology available in the classroom, such as computers, projectors, or even radio.

Implementing affordable mobile learning activities

As stated previously, many EFL learners from low socio-economic status (SES) may not afford sophisticated devices typically used in mobile learning environments, like iPods, PDAs and smart phones. Thus, conventional cell phones provide affordable opportunities for mobile learning activities in the EFL classroom. In Latin American developing countries, low SES people do not interact with mobile devices in the same way as middle and high SES people do. Because of financial factors as the main reason, the former often opt for prepaid conventional cell phones using mostly voice and text, the basic features (Galperin & Mariscal, 2007; Galperin, 2010). Consequently, English language teachers must prepare activities that are applicable to their context, and can be performed within their capabilities. Short-message-service (SMS), picture camera, Bluetooth, audio and video are basic features available in most conventional cell phones and are suitable for language learning activities (Cavus & Ibrahim, 2007; Lu, 2008; Cooney & Keogh, 2007). Teachers can use conventional cell phone features to develop affordable mobile learning activities in the following ways:

Short message service (SMS)

As seen in previous sections, the SMS feature has been utilized in mobile learning studies to send quizzes, mini lessons, and vocabulary words to students. In most cases, these have been sent with programs designed for the purpose of the studies. If an English language teacher working with low SES students wants to make use of this feature, even with the most inexpensive rates, delivering multiple SMS on a regular basis may become an economical burden.

Many EFL teachers can access internet to work on their lesson plans from the computer labs in their schools. Some teachers have their own laptops or desktop computers from where they prepare their class material looking for additional resources online. Internet provides with alternatives that teachers can utilize to send students information through text messages. Several free online group-messaging services can be used in Latin American countries, making possible the delivery of class material or information to students' cell phones. Teachers can use these websites to send short messages containing new vocabulary words for review and reinforcement, as well as reminders about pending assignments. Cell phones SMS feature can be also utilized for students to receive short quizzes (Ekong, 2008) sent through computer software programs that can be downloaded from the internet for a very low price. These software programs are usually offered on trial periods that allow teachers to experiment before fully implementing them with the students.

Picture camera

Proper use of cell phone pictures can enhance students' understanding and retention of new vocabulary (Basoglu & Akdemir, 2010). In EFL beginner and low-intermediate levels, cell phone camera pictures can be used in lieu of picture cards to help students reinforce new vocabulary words. When learning new words on certain topic, students are usually limited to the vocabulary in their books, with little opportunity to learn vocabulary about their surroundings.

Besides using with the course book material, students working on parts of the house vocabulary can use their cell phones to take pictures in different part of their homes and in the following class they exchange the pictures via Bluetooth, or transfer it to the class room computer (if available). Students can then take turns to describe what they see in the pictures, either orally or writing sentences.

Graphic representations permit learners to work with events, places and objects missing in time and place (Norman, 1993). A typical assignment in EFL classroom for writing activities is having students write a paragraph or a short composition of what they do or where they go over the holidays. Students can use their cell phones to take pictures of places they visit over the weekends or holidays, and later show them as a slideshow in the computer to the teacher and classmates, while reading about the places in the pictures and what they did in those places. Depending on the capability of the cell phone and the options for the student, a variation of the activity could be using mms or Bluetooth to send the teacher and other classmates (if in the classroom), a picture of a holiday vacation with a short description of it.

This cell phone feature can be used to create fun learning activities to reinforce students' vocabulary learning, writing and speaking skills, but there is a disadvantage to consider. As stated earlier, the EFL teacher and students need to make use of what is available in their learning context for an effective mobile learning experience. Many schools in developing countries cannot provide all classrooms with technology; thus, some activities with cell phones cameras would not be suitable if other technological resources, such as a computer, are missing in the classroom. In this case, if there are not other alternative activities with this feature, the teacher would decide to give up its use.

Audio and video recording

Audio and video features have a great potential as tools in EFL activities, since students can use them to practice listening and speaking skills (Kukulsma-Hulme,

2008). For example, with the audio recording feature, students can record an English speaking activity, such as introducing themselves, interviewing an English speaking person or reporting on an event. The recording can be transferred to a computer if it is available in the classroom, or a radio with usb port to be listened by the teacher for assessment and by classmates for listening comprehension. Similarly, with the video recording feature, students can act out in groups, recording dialogues in English about a topic of their interest. The recording can be transferred to the classroom computer to be watched by the rest of the class and evaluated by the teacher.

Bluetooth

This short-range feature is available in almost any conventional cell phone, and represents an inexpensive alternative to exchange and share class material. As seen in the previous examples, this feature is useful to transfer pictures, video and audio files from a cell phone to another cell phone or a computer. The main drawback of this feature is that devices exchanging information should be relatively close, which restricts its functionality. However, this limitation can be used to promote team work and collaboration among students.

Advantages and disadvantages of conventional cell phones as teaching tools

Mobile learning introduced new modalities in teaching and learning that are accompanied by many benefits, but also by many challenges. The use of cell phones as language teaching tools presents advantages and disadvantages that should be considered.

Advantages

These are some advantages in using cell phones as teaching tools:

- Affordable, small size and lightweight. Their low cost, small size and

portability (Cui & Wang, 2008; Lu, 2008). Cell phones allow access to other type of connectivity besides internet, like infra-red, Blue-tooth, which are usually inexpensive and easy to use (Csete, Wong & Vogel, 2008).

- **Motivating and engaging.** Cell phone use in mobile learning may increase teen learners' motivation and engagement in learning a new language. Their use in language teaching opens doors to a new learning environment for learners (Stockwell, 2010), where students can experience different ways to learn a new language, using a familiar device.
- **Complement traditional language teaching.** With the adequate design of instruction, cell phones provide relatively inexpensive m-learning opportunities, as well as situated learning experiences (Elias, 2011). Their use can complement language teaching material and resources inside the classroom and therefore contribute to the achievement of the learning objectives.
- **Flexibility of time and place.** Cell phones enable both teachers and students to take English language learning out of the physical classroom space. Students can receive reinforcement of new vocabulary material taught in class while they are out of school. (Lu, 2008; Kukulska-Hulme & Shield, 2008).
- **Collaborative learning and teamwork.** When using cell phones, students can engage in class activities and teamwork in higher cognitive levels than traditional teaching methods do (Kukulska-Hulme, 2006). Mobile learning activities also encourage interaction between teachers and students while working in group activities in the classroom, making learning more meaningful and the instruction more learner-centered.

Disadvantages

Cell phones also have some limitations used as teaching tools:

- Small screens and keypad. These aspects can make cell phones difficult to use for instruction. A small screen size reduces the display of information, and a small keypad makes the input of data difficult (Sharples, 2006; Shudong, & Higgins, 2006).
- Primary purpose. For teenagers and young adults, cell phones' primary use is not for learning but for communication and entertainment (Cui & Wang, 2008; Stockwell, 2010). That is, students usually have access to mobile features and applications that are not designed to teach. This might be a challenge for their use in the classroom. Some students would find difficult to see their devices as learning tools, feeling reluctant to use it for this purpose.
- Disruptive devices. In many classrooms, it is assumed that cell phones represent a tool for distraction, disruption and cheating (Domitrek & Raby, 2008). The access to games and texting during classes are the most common disruptive activities among adolescent students, whereas adult learners might take instruction time to use their cell phones for personal or work purposes (Meurant, 2007; Ekong, 2008). These types of situations have led some institutions to restrict or completely ban cell phone use inside the classroom.
- Pedagogical implications. Teachers may have to deal with the pedagogical implications of using mobile devices in instruction (Shudong, & Higgins, 2006). Although some educators may find mobile devices very innovative and motivating teaching tools, others would be skeptical about their use, either for the extra time spent in planning and designing the activity or for the lack of familiarity with this technology.

Recommendations

In comparison with other learning modalities, mobile learning is just getting started and still requires more research to fully exploit the benefits that it can offer (Saran et al, 2008). Recommendations for future implementation on affordable mobile learning and a better use of cell phones as teaching tools are worth pursuing. First of all, teachers are responsible to integrate mobile learning into the classroom, thus will need to understand how to implement these mobile technologies in their teaching. Cui and Wang (2008) recommended that teachers receive the necessary training to use this technology in their classroom and how to employ it properly with the students. In addition, even when mobile learning has had a great impact and success in the educational field, educators cannot rely only on technology to guarantee learning. Teachers and students' determination and zeal is necessary to achieve the learning goal (Cooney & Keogh, 2007). Learning with mobile devices cannot substitute classroom learning approaches, but it can complement and add value to classroom activities (Motiwalla, 2007). Mobile learning is not meant to replace conventional teaching-learning methods; its purpose is to help improve students' learning in a new and exciting way.

Conclusion

Mobile devices have contributed to make learning ubiquitous. This factor has become a challenge to educators and has made them rethink some current teaching approaches (Elias, 2011). The inclusion of cell phones as teaching tools inside and outside the classroom has helped to increase students motivation to learn and has opened new doors for teachers to explore new ways to enhance learning (Corbeil & Valdez-Corbeil, 2007). As discussed previously, research in mobile learning has yielded positive results in its implementation in language teaching in developed and developing countries across East Asia, Europe and Africa. Nevertheless, the mobile learning phenomenon in English language teaching is little known in developing countries in Latin America. It is necessary

to promote it throughout the different educational levels, so that educators be aware of all the benefits of this learning modality, of course, adapted to the reality of Latin American cultures in economic and social aspects. Conventional cell phones' features represent an affordable option for English language teachers who want to implement mobile learning strategies in their classroom, but facing students' limitations in affording expensive and sophisticated mobile devices.

The aim of this paper was to find out and discuss the possibilities of conventional cell phones' application for educational purposes, specifically in EFL. However, the use of mobile learning in language teaching cannot be considered separate from traditional teaching methods, but as a complement to them. Its effectiveness will depend on how teachers decide to integrate it once they have identified the students' needs. Further research is needed in order to study in more depth the pedagogical implications of cell phone use as teaching tools for EFL teaching, taking into account the learners' needs, socio-economic status and what type of technologies to which students have access.

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